

Mapping Global Parkinson's Disease Data: Toward the Development of the PARKINSON BRASIL National Database

Fernanda Naves A. P. Mascarenhas
Faculdade de Engenharia Elétrica
Universidade Federal de Uberlândia
Uberlândia, Brazil
ORCID: 0000-0002-3799-5844

Nívea Maria Machado Leite
Faculdade de Engenharia Elétrica
Universidade Federal de Uberlândia
Uberlândia, Brazil
ORCID: 0009-0003-9678-2843

Luanne Cardoso Mendes
Faculdade de Engenharia Elétrica
Universidade Federal de Uberlândia
Uberlândia, Brazil
ORCID: 0000-0001-7465-9332

Pedro Henrique Bernardes C. Milken
Faculdade de Engenharia Elétrica
Universidade Federal de Uberlândia
Uberlândia, Brazil
ORCID: 0009-0000-9801-7086

Maria Olívia Domingos Rezio Ramos
Faculdade de Engenharia Elétrica
Universidade Federal de Uberlândia
Uberlândia, Brazil
ORCID: 0000-0001-9240-523X

Adriano de Oliveira Andrade
Faculdade de Engenharia Elétrica
Universidade Federal de Uberlândia
Uberlândia, Brazil
ORCID: 0000-0002-5689-6606

Camille Marques Alves
Faculdade de Engenharia Elétrica
Universidade Federal de Uberlândia
Uberlândia, Brazil
ORCID: 0000-0002-7509-1547

Ariana Moura Cabral
Faculdade de Engenharia Elétrica
Universidade Federal de Uberlândia
Uberlândia, Brazil
ORCID: 0000-0002-9804-353X

Abstract— Parkinson's disease (PD) represents a growing global public health challenge, exacerbated by the lack of structured and accessible data in Brazil. This study conducted a descriptive and exploratory analysis of 55 publicly or partially accessible PD-related datasets, aiming to map their key characteristics, data modalities, geographic distribution, and access conditions. Movement signals, clinical data and biomarkers were the most prevalent types, reflecting advances in monitoring technologies and the ongoing relevance of traditional assessments. Most datasets originate from developed countries, highlighting disparities in access to information and scientific output. The PARKINSON BRASIL project emerges as a strategic initiative to address national data gaps by developing a comprehensive, open-access database tailored to the Brazilian context. The findings underscore the potential of multimodal approaches and machine learning in PD research, while reinforcing the importance of data transparency and sharing to support progress in precision medicine.

Keywords— Parkinson's disease, Biomedical databases, Multimodal analysis, Machine learning, National database.

I. INTRODUCTION

Parkinson's disease (PD) is considered the second most prevalent neurodegenerative disease worldwide. It can affect individuals in their productive years, starting between 40 and 50 years of age, significantly compromising their quality of life and aging process [1].

In Brazil, reporting of PD cases is not mandatory, meaning that healthcare professionals and services are not required to notify health authorities upon diagnosing new cases. Consequently, the actual number of individuals with PD in the country is unknown and must be estimated. Current estimates suggest around 220,000 patients, based on epidemiological projections, and international studies suggest that this number may more than double by 2030 [2].

PD poses an increasing global public health challenge, requiring a comprehensive understanding of its clinical, epidemiological, motor, and non-motor dimensions to improve research and formulate effective treatments. The lack of comprehensive and organized data in Brazil represents a significant shortcoming, hindering both research capacity and the formulation of health initiatives targeted to the Brazilian population [3].

In this context, it becomes essential to compare and analyze available information from comprehensive global databases, aiming to identify effective strategies for addressing PD. Additionally, it is crucial to map and describe the main international databases currently available on the disease. A thorough analysis of data categories, scope, and frequency not only highlights gaps and weaknesses in these systems but also reveals the scarcity of Brazil-specific data, which compromises the formulation of effective public policies and the advancement of national research [4].

Although international initiatives on PD exist, there is a substantial lack of structured and publicly accessible data in the Brazilian context. This gap limits our understanding of disease progression in the Brazilian population and hinders the proposal of appropriate strategies for diagnosis, treatment, and follow-up [4].

PARKINSON BRASIL is a research project dedicated to filling critical gaps in existing databases on PD, with a focus on the Brazilian reality. Its primary objective is to develop a comprehensive national database on PD that serves as a primary resource for researchers, healthcare professionals, and policymakers. This is a cross-sectional observational study with a control group, designed to construct, validate, and implement an innovative database capable of integrating clinical, epidemiological, motor, and non-motor information related to PD.

The database will be made available to the national and international academic community, aiming to foster advancements in PD research. The project includes the collection of paired data from both a control group and an experimental group, using structured questionnaires, standardized motor tasks, and validated clinical scales. All data will be anonymized to ensure participant privacy and securely stored in designated repositories. Quantitative, qualitative, and descriptive factors will be analyzed to characterize and distinguish the studied groups. The results obtained will contribute to a better understanding of the stages of PD, considering epidemiological, motor, and non-motor aspects, and will support the development of technologies and methodologies applicable to clinical practice.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

This study conducted a descriptive and exploratory analysis of public or partially accessible databases related to PD. Data collection was structured based on a spreadsheet developed by the authors, comprising 55 database records identified between the years 2008 and 2024. The dataset is available on the Zenodo platform [5], under the digital identifier (DOI) <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16451705>.

A. Data collection

The spreadsheet was built through systematic searches conducted in public repositories, biomedical research portals (such as NIH RePORTER, PubMed, Data.gov), academic platforms (such as Kaggle, PhysioNet, Synapse, NeuroVault), and institutional websites linked to specific initiatives (such as the Michael J. Fox Foundation, the Global Parkinson's Genetics Program, and the Parkinson's

Disease – Drug Acceleration Partnership). Only datasets that provided minimum information on access, population description, and types of available data were included. Each row in the spreadsheet represents a distinct dataset, organized according to the following variables:

- Name of the dataset;
- Acronym (when available);
- Year of release;
- Country or countries involved;
- Types of available data (clinical, genetic, neuroimaging, sensor-based, among others);
- Official access link;
- Number and type of groups evaluated;
- Main variables collected;
- Associated scientific publications (when identified);
- Type of access to the dataset (open, upon request, or restricted).

B. Data processing and classification

The data classification was conducted manually, based on the descriptions available on the official websites of the datasets. The category “Parkinson’s Disease Data (standardized label)” was divided into five main classes: clinical, genetic, biomarkers, movement/sensor signals, and neuroimaging. Datasets that included multiple types of data were assigned to more than one category.

Missing fields were completed through supplementary manual searches using search engines (Google Scholar, Scopus, PubMed), including the identification of associated publications and methodological information available in user guides or dataset documentation.

C. Data analysis

Descriptive statistical analysis was performed using Microsoft Excel (Microsoft Corp., Redmond, WA) and the Python programming language (pandas, seaborn, and matplotlib libraries). The following results were generated:

- Frequency distributions by country, year, and type of data;
- Visualizations by thematic category;
- Bar and pie charts illustrating types of access;
- Exploratory analysis of the relationship between the year of dataset creation and the volume of associated scientific publications.

The presentation of results aimed to highlight the diversity and accessibility of currently available PD

datasets, emphasizing opportunities for collaborative and reproducible research.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. General vision of the dataset

Fifty-five public or partially accessible databases related to PD were analyzed. These repositories were categorized according to their country of origin, the type of data collected, and access conditions.

Over the years, there has been a progressive increase in the availability of datasets focused on Parkinson's disease research (Fig. 1), with notable periods during which the number of new initiatives increased significantly.

The substantial growth in the availability of PD data in recent years contrasts with the increase in hospitalization and mortality rates associated with the disease [6]. This scenario reflects, on the one hand, advances in data acquisition technologies and, on the other, the growing global interest in the application of artificial intelligence in healthcare [7].

This duality highlights the crucial importance of comprehensive and integrated data systems—not only for documenting the epidemiological reality but also for informing effective strategies to improve health outcomes.

Despite the length of time, initiatives aimed at consolidating a database on Parkinson's disease in Brazil are minimal. This gap compromises epidemiological monitoring, the formulation of specific public policies, and the development of clinical and translational research adapted to the Brazilian reality. In this context, the **PARKINSON BRASIL** project was created to meet this need, promoting the organization, integration, and accessibility of national data related to the disease. This work has already been approved by the Research Ethics Committee of the Federal University of Uberlandia (81274724.0.0000.5152), approved by the EBSEH hospital network (13585), and registered in Clinical Trials (NCT06536348) [8].

Fig. 1 – Number of databases per year.

B. Geographical distribution of the data

The geographic distribution (Fig. 2) reveals a significant concentration of datasets originating from developed countries, with the United States standing out. This predominance may be linked to higher research investment and the infrastructure required for the collection and sharing of clinical data.

The United States leads in scientific and technological output—in 2021 alone, 525 patents related to Parkinson's disease were registered. This scenario highlights a possible correlation between data availability and scientific and technological advancement in the field [9].

An analysis of the graph (Fig. 2) highlights a scarcity of databases from developing countries. Although the results of this research identify some national initiatives, they are fragmented, with limited geographic coverage and data focused on motor signs. In this context, the **PARKINSON BRASIL** project emerges as a structured proposal to mitigate these limitations by creating a national, integrated, decentralized, and open-access database. The initiative covers three Brazilian states and incorporates a broad spectrum of variables, including clinical, socioeconomic, cognitive, motor, and non-motor symptom data, as well as specific assessments, aiming to provide a more comprehensive and robust representation of the reality of Parkinson's disease in the country.

Fig. 2 – Bases distribution per country.

C. Data type

Regarding the types of data made available, movement signals, clinical data, and biomarkers are the most prevalent in the analyzed datasets (Fig. 3). This reflects a growing interest in the objective quantification of both motor and non-motor symptoms of Parkinson’s disease. Movement signals appear in over 30% of datasets, indicating a strong emphasis on sensor-based and wearable technologies for capturing motor fluctuations [10].

The substantial presence of clinical and biomarker data highlights the continued relevance of traditional assessments. At the same time, the significant proportion of data containing sensory and voice signals highlights a growing trend toward integrating non-invasive digital biomarkers into disease monitoring and diagnosis. Most studies still use established diagnostic criteria, reinforcing the importance of traditional clinical assessments—such as medical history, assessment of motor symptoms, and response to levodopa—with some biomarkers used as supplements [11].

Although genetic data appears in a smaller share compared to the top categories, its presence remains significant. This aligns with the rising investment in gene therapy and personalized medicine for Parkinson’s disease, as highlighted by recent literature [12].

The diversity of data modalities available—including drawing tasks, medical imaging, brain signals, and sensor data—suggests great potential for multimodal analyses. Such integrative approaches can enhance the development of predictive and diagnostic models by leveraging complementary sources of information. This richness of data types is key to building more robust and generalizable machine learning models, ultimately supporting precision medicine efforts in Parkinson’s research [13].

There are significant limitations in the currently available Brazilian databases, which focus predominantly on motor parameters. In this context, the **PARKINSON**

BRASIL project aims to overcome these structural limitations by gathering individual data obtained through standardized and validated instruments, including socioeconomic information, clinical data, medications in use, motor and non-motor symptoms, cognitive impairments, depression profiles, as well as specific assessments related to dysarthria and fine motor skills—including head, neck, and eye movements, facial expressions, and motor coordination. This initiative aims not only to strengthen national scientific production but also to expand Brazil’s representation in international multicentre studies through a comprehensive, multimodal, and decentralized database.

Fig. 3 - Types of databases.

D. Access type

Regarding the type of access (Fig. 4), most of the analyzed datasets offer free, public, or open access. This model is extremely important because it democratizes scientific knowledge, increases transparency in research, and fosters technology development, as it facilitates data reuse and fosters a collaborative environment conducive to innovation [14]. However, a considerable portion of the datasets still require controlled access, involving formal requests and ethics approval. This limitation can hinder the reproducibility and comparability of studies.

In this context, **PARKINSON BRASIL**’s initiative to create an open database aligns with this trend, the promotion of which is essential for the advancement of science.

Fig. 4 – Distribution per access type.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

The relationship between the growth of datasets and scientific progress in the field of Parkinson's disease highlights the direct connection between research and development. In this context, the creation of a unified national database stands out as a crucial step toward mapping the Brazilian reality and supporting studies specifically focused on our population.

The proposal of the **PARKINSON BRASIL** project—to develop an open, nationwide database—is therefore essential to strengthen scientific production in the country, enhance Brazil's representation in international studies, and contribute to advances in diagnosis, treatment, and potentially, in reducing disease-related mortality.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

"The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest".

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Enter the information of the corresponding author:

Author: Fernanda Naves A. P. Mascarenhas
 Institute: Faculty of Electrical Engineering (FEELT)
 Street: UFU Campus Santa Mônica, Bloco 1A, Sala 1A216, Av. João Naves de Ávila, 2121, Bairro Santa Mônica, CEP: 38408-100.
 City: Uberlândia; Country: Brazil
 E-mail: mascarenhas.nutri@hotmail.com